

TFAW K2 survey: an insight into a few hundreds of new Earth-sized planetary candidates

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Abstract

Kepler’s extended mission (K2) Earth-sized planetary legacy is a niche that still remains to be fully exploited. We reanalyzed all light curves in K2 C1-C8, C12-C18 campaigns with a wavelet-based detrending method TFAW developed by our team, and the period search algorithm TLS. The combination of these two methods allows to detect and characterize planetary transit candidates around fainter targets ($12.5 < K_p < 18.5$) than any previous study. We present 220 new planetary candidates as a result of a preliminary survey. All of them have passed a vetting procedure including: candidate periods with $SDE_{\text{TLS}} > 9.0$, visual inspection of the candidate light curve, inspection of archival Pan-STARRS1 images and Gaia DR2 to discard close stellar companions and statistical $\text{FPP} < 2\%$. We assigned our candidates sample three levels of priority: six top-priority detected in two or more separate but overlapping K2 campaigns, 110 high-priority meeting the above requirements, and 104 low-priority still meeting the same requirements, but having either FPP close to 2% or pending further reanalysis. The bulk of our TFAW K2 survey are small planet candidates with $R_p < 2R_{\oplus}$, most of them orbiting faint low-mass stars. Our survey adds new candidates to different areas of interest in exoplanetary science: several dozens in the small planet radius gap, four in the Hot-Super-Earths desert, and a few in the Ultra-Short-Period planets. We also present six candidates within the Habitable Zones of their host stars.

1 Introduction

Current K2 mission legacy is admirable: 443 confirmed planets with K2 light curves for stellar host, 426 confirmed planets exclusively discovered from K2 observations (44 with radii smaller than $1.25 R_{\oplus}$), and 889 candidates yet to be confirmed. Data analysis has played a key role in increasing these counts of confirmed and planetary candidates. The first paradigmatic example was the series of pixel decorrelation and detrending algorithms which culminated in the EVEREST 2.0 pipeline (Luger *et al.*, 2018), not only providing the best photometric precision from archived K2 light curves at the moment, but also recovering original Kepler-like photometric precision down to $K_p=15$ mag. With these EVEREST 2.0 light curves, most planet searches were conducted in all K2 campaigns, yielding an appreciable fraction of the current confirmed planets and candidates (Crossfield *et al.*, 2016; Vanderburg *et al.*, 2016; Mayo *et al.*, 2018). The next step forward in recent K2 planet searches, such as Kruse *et al.* (2019); Heller *et al.* (2019), defined statistically robust vetting procedures to diminishing the false positive probability due to non-associated blended eclipsing binaries, eclipsing binaries, hierarchical triples and non-associated stars with transiting planets. Also, Heller *et al.* (2019) was especially sensitive to Earth-sized planets given that the authors used the Transit Least Squares (TLS) algorithm (Hippke & Heller, 2019) as a new transit detection tool, which is optimized to detect these small planets.

2 TFAW, transit search & vetting

Our team has developed a novel wavelet-based detrending and denosing algorithm called TFAW (del Ser *et al.*, 2018). Using the Stationary Wavelet Transform (SWT), TFAW is able to denoise and reconstruct the input signal without making any feature assumption or modifying any of its astrophysical properties.

The detrending and denoising procedure can be summarized as follows: 1) using a template of reference light curves, trends and systematics are removed from the target light curve, 2) the underlying signal shape is inferred by means of the SWT. The outliers and a first estimation of the high frequency noise contribution are removed, 3) frequency analysis step: a search for periodic signals is run over this outlier-free and denoised signal, 4) if a significant periodicity is found, the shape of the trend- and noise-free phase folded signal is estimated using the SWT, and 5) signal reconstruction step: the light curve is iteratively denoised and reconstructed.

As shown in del Ser & Fors (2020), TFAW delivers both better photometric precision and planet characterization than any previous detrending method applied to K2 light curves. The increased photometric precision achieved with TFAW, specially for faint K2 magnitudes, together with TLS improved capabilities to detect small planets, enable us to detect new, smaller than or Earth-sized planets orbiting G-, K- and M-type stars, missed by former studies.

We follow a transit search, vetting, and False-Positive Probability (FPP) approach similar to the one detailed in Heller *et al.* (2019). We have extended TFAW’s capabilities

to detect transits of smaller planets by using TLS during the frequency analysis step. TLS is run using updated modelled stellar parameters, M_s , R_s , T_{eff} , $\log g$, and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$, obtained from Hardegree-Ullman *et al.* (2020) and stellar quadratic limb-darkening coefficients (u_1 , and u_2) as computed by Claret (2018). We consider a detection to be significant if its peak in the TLS power spectrum has a Signal Detection Efficiency (SDE_{TLS}) value above 9.0 (false-positive rate $<10^{-4}$ (Hippke & Heller, 2019)). Any light curve that matches this criteria during TFAW’s signal detection step undergoes the full signal reconstruction and denoising procedure.

Our vetting procedure follows the next steps: First, we visually inspect all significant TFAW-corrected light curves and only keep those which show transit-like features. We cross-match them with the most up-to-date (January 2021) lists of confirmed or candidate exoplanets from the NASA Exoplanet Archive ¹ or in the VizieR database. All transits are required to be at least 0.5 days away from the beginning or end of any gaps in their light curves to avoid false positives. For long period candidates, with four or fewer transits present in the light curve, they should have a signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) >10 . In addition, the average depth of the odd/even transits should agree within $<3\sigma$ and secondary eclipses at half an orbital phase after the candidate transit should not present at the $>3\sigma$ level. We also rule out that no other light curve in the same CCD module present transit-like features with similar periods and transit epochs as the candidate. We compare the TLS periodograms before and after applying TFAW to check if they present similar peaks. We also inspect independent photometry and high angular resolution images to evaluate contamination from other sources. Finally, we use the publicly available *vespa*² software (Morton, 2012) to evaluate the FPP of our transit candidates. We supply the software with the TFAW phase folded light curves of our candidates, their celestial coordinates, the stellar parameters of their host star, and its photometry. We also compute a limiting aperture obtained from the EVEREST 2 . 0 database. Using such information, *vespa* calculates the probabilities of the transiting signal being caused by non-associated blended eclipsing binaries, eclipsing binaries, hierarchical triples and non-associated stars with transiting planets. Only candidates with a FPP lower than 2% are considered valid candidates.

3 Current status of the TFAW K2 survey

TFAW opens a new niche for exoplanetary candidate search, allowing to detect transiting objects around fainter stars than any other previous survey (see Figure 1 top-left plot). We present a set of 220 new K2 single-planetary system candidates. This is a preliminary set of results from the TFAW K2 survey: an ongoing, uniform reanalysis of $\sim 300\text{K}$ EVEREST 2 . 0-corrected light curves from K2 campaigns C1-C8 and C12-C18 to search for new, previously undetected, single- and multiple-planetary systems candidates. All of our candidates have undergone the detection and vetting procedure described in Section 2 and have a *vespa*-FPP lower than 2%. We have classified them in three priority ranks using the following criteria: 6 top-priority candidates detected in two or more separate but overlapping K2 cam-

paigns, 110 high-priority candidates meeting all the vetting requirements, and 104 low-priority ones that, still meet the same requirements but have either FPP close to 2%, SDE_{TLS} close to 9.0 or need further reanalysis. A summary of our results is shown in Figure 1. The bulk (78.6%) of our TFAW K2 survey candidates are small planets with $R_p < 2R_{\oplus}$, most of them orbiting faint low-mass stars. Our survey adds new candidates to different areas of interest in exoplanetary science: four candidates (one with high priority) within the Hot-Super-Earth desert and six new Ultra-Short-Period (USP) candidates (four ranked as high priority). We add 40 new candidates (one of them ranked as top priority) within the K2 small planet radius gap ($1.5R_{\oplus} < R_p < 2R_{\oplus}$ sample). We also present six new candidates (two of them ranked as high priority) within the Habitable Zones (HZ) of their host stars. Four of them in the conservative HZ and the other two within the conservative HZ limits.

3.1 EPIC 248828117.02: a new Earth-sized candidate from C14

EPIC 248828117 is a $K_p = 12.915 \pm 0.046$ mag, $G = 12.8907 \pm 0.0004$ mag (Gaia Collaboration *et al.*, 2018) and $K_s = 11.435 \pm 0.023$ mag star. It is located at $(\alpha, \delta) = (10:20:49.11, +11:21:32.07)$ (Gaia Collaboration *et al.*, 2018) and observed by the K2 mission during the C14 monitoring campaign.

Table 1: Stellar parameters for EPIC 248828117 host star, TLS-detection parameters for the transit planetary candidate EPIC 248828117.02.

Stellar parameters	
Stellar radius R_s (R_{\odot})	$0.947^{+0.061}_{-0.057}$
Stellar mass M_s (M_{\odot})	$0.835^{+0.356}_{-0.250}$
Effective temperature (K)	5714 ± 138
Metallicity $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$	-0.199 ± 0.235
Distance (pc)	$398.12^{+7.86}_{-7.57}$
Spectral type	G3
TLS-detection transit parameters	
Period P (days)	2.896 ± 0.008
Epoch T_0 (BJD-2454833) (days)	3074.67171218
Duration (hours)	2.58
Depth δ (per cent)	0.016 ± 0.002
Radius ratio p	0.01228
Scaled semimajor axis a (au)	0.03748 ± 0.00007
Planetary radius R_p (R_{\oplus})	1.27 ± 0.08
SDE_{TLS}	14.943

Table 1 lists the catalogued stellar parameters by Hardegree-Ullman *et al.* (2020) and the transit parameters obtained with TLS. In addition, Gaia Collaboration (Gaia Collaboration *et al.*, 2018) provides a $T_{\text{eff}} = 5753^{+313}_{-98}$ K, which is compatible within the previous listed value. No variability detection for this star is provided either in Armstrong, D. J. *et al.* (2015) or Armstrong *et al.* (2016).

Normalized phase-folded light curve in Table 2 illustrates the noise filtering efficiency of TFAW. For EPIC 248828117.02, using TLS estimated transit parameters, TFAW yields a $1.27 \pm 0.08 R_{\oplus}$ planet orbiting its host star at 0.03748 ± 0.00007 au with a period of 2.896 ± 0.008 d.

¹<https://exoplanetarchive.ipac.caltech.edu>

²<https://github.com/timothymorton/VESPA>

Figure 1: TFAW K2 survey summary. Top left: Host star K_p magnitude vs measured transit depth. Top right: planetary radius R_p/R_\oplus vs insolation flux S/S_\oplus . Faint yellow area comprises the Hot-Super-Earth desert. Bottom left: stellar effective temperature $T_{\text{eff}}(K)$ vs insolation flux S/S_\oplus . Zoom-in corresponds to the approximate Habitable Zone limits. Bottom right: TFAW K2 survey summary histograms where we highlight our candidates contribution to the USP and small planet radius gap sample.

4 Conclusions & Future work

The current status of the TFAW K2 survey conducted over all light curves in C1-C8, C12-C18 campaigns is shown. 220 new single-planetary candidates are detected, visually inspected, vetted, and *vespa* statistically validated. We present EPIC 248828117.02 as an illustrative example of the TFAW survey potential for detecting Earth-sized planets orbiting solar type stars.

Our survey fills a niche missed by previous transit searches: smaller than or Earth-sized planets orbiting G-, K- and M-type stars as faint as $12.5 < K_p < 18.5$.

Most, but not exclusively, of our new planetary candidates are small ($R_p < 2R_\oplus$) orbiting faint M-dwarfs. We add six new candidates in the USP planets, we contribute with four new ones in the Hot-Super-Earths desert, and we duplicate (by adding 40 new ones) the sample of candidates within the small planet radius gap ($1.5R_\oplus < R_p < 2.0R_\oplus$). Importantly, six of our six candidates lie within the HZ (four conservative HZ and two optimistic HZ) of their host stars.

An extension of the TFAW K2 survey for detecting multi-planetary candidates is underway.

TESS has already (during Cycles 1, 3) and will (during Cy-

cle 4) overlap K2 campaigns. Thus, with our current knowledge of the K2 planetary candidates from TFAW survey, we can use TESS to follow up the brightest and/or deepest transit candidates. Also, candidates ephemeris are updated to TESS epoch. We have already initiated this task for those candidates with TESS data available. We employ the TESS QLP light curves (Huang *et al.*, 2020), with photometric precision in the order of $\sim 0.1\text{ppt}$ for $T_{\text{mag}} \sim 12$. As we performed in TFAW survey for K2 light curves, we will apply the TFAW detrending method to improve the nominal TESS QLP precision.

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Figure 2: Normalized phase-folded EPIC 248828117.02 light curve with TLS model data marked in red for EVEREST 2.0 (left), TFAW's frequency analysis step (middle) and for the TFAW-reconstructed signal (right). Blue represents the binned data.

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